

MODERN REQUIREMENTS FOR ORGANIZING THE PROCESS OF TRAINING AS A MEANS OF DEVELOPMENT AND FORMATION OF PERSONALITY

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***Abstract.** The article reveals the characteristic features of the educational process as a factor influencing the development and formation of personality. The functions of the learning process are also described.*

***Keywords:** education, training, learning process, educational functions.*

Radical, socio-economic, organizational transformations taking place in society objectively require significant changes in the system of lifelong education of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Preparing the younger generation for life in new socio-economic conditions and forms of economic management requires special preparation from teachers for lessons. The significant difficulties that have arisen for graduates when entering universities, technical schools, and colleges place high demands on their general labor training. A significant place in the training of future generalist specialists is given to general technical subjects. General technical training is the most important component of polytechnic education. In a comprehensive school, the basis of polytechnic education is the educational program “Technology”. One of the main objectives of this course is to develop technical knowledge among students. The formation of technical knowledge is a very complex process that requires mutual work between the teacher and students. It requires great professionalism from the teacher and interest in the student’s knowledge. The better the teacher knows his subject, effectively uses methods and forms of communicating new knowledge, studies and analyzes new technologies for the formation of technical knowledge, the more interest students will show in this subject.

The process of teaching general technical subjects is an integral system. It is possible to characterize the learning process as a system only in the dynamics of conducting classes, tracing its composition (elements), structure (connections) in accordance with functions.

Particular attention is paid to the organization of the educational process of teaching general technical subjects in higher educational institutions based on the following didactic principles:

- integrity in the unity of learning and teaching, the unification of knowledge, skills and abilities into a worldview system;
- systematic, comprehensive;
- purposefulness and orderliness;
- dynamism;
- uncertainty of the result.

The educational (didactic) process contains the following main links of interaction:

Learning functions - displaying object properties. Functions characterize the essence of the learning process. There are three functions: teaching, developing, educational.

Activities of a teacher	Activities of trainees
Clarification by students of the goals and objectives of learning	Own activities to create positive motivation for learning
Familiarization of students with new knowledge (phenomena, events, objects, laws)	Perception of new knowledge and skills
Managing the process of awareness and acquisition of knowledge and skills	Analysis, synthesis, comparison, comparison, systematization
Managing the process of transition from theory to practice	Acquisition of skills and abilities, their systematization
Organization of heuristic and research activities	Practical activities to independently solve emerging problems
Checking and assessing measurements in student learning and development	Self-control, self-diagnosis of achievements

To organize an effective educational process, the following preparation is required:

1. two-way mutual understanding between the teacher and students;
2. organization of joint activities of teachers and students.
3. in the educational process, create stimulation and motivation in the activities of students.
4. create conditions for the development of students' creative abilities.
5. observe consistency in the organization and management of the educational process.
6. maintain the integrity and unity of goals, means, and learning outcomes.
7. comply with age-related norms.
8. organization of the educational process with the aim of developing professional skills, as well as instilling in students responsibility for future professional activities.

Educational functions. They lie in the fact that the learning process is aimed at the formation of knowledge, abilities, skills, worldview and experience of creative activity. What is important is that the knowledge gained must be complete, consistent, meaningful and effective.

Developmental functions. This means that in the learning process the student develops in all directions: the development of speech, thinking, sensory, motor, emotional-volitional needs and motivational spheres of the individual. Educational functions. It consists of the formation of moral and aesthetic ideas, a system of views on the world, the ability to follow the norms of behavior in society, and comply with the laws adopted in it. To understand the role of learning as a means of development and personality formation, it is of great importance that this process is not limited only to the mastery of knowledge by students, the development of practical knowledge and skills. Training has a broader developmental and formative impact on the individual. Knowledge as a subject of acquisition has 3 interconnected aspects:

1. Theoretical.
2. Practical.
3. Worldview and moral.

With proper training, students master all three aspects of the material.

The developmental and educational-formative influence of training on the individual led to the emergence in pedagogy of a special concept denoting this process. This process is called education. Education should be understood as a person's mastery of a certain system of scientific knowledge, practical skills and abilities and associated with them one or another level of development of his mental, cognitive and creative activity, as well as moral and aesthetic culture, which together determine his social appearance and individual identity. Education as a concept includes, on the one hand, the process of mastering the material being studied, i.e. learning, and on the other hand, the educational and formative influence of this process on the individual, personifying their unity and organic interconnection. And when didactics is sometimes defined as a theory of learning and education, they thereby want to emphasize that it explores both the theoretical foundations of the learning process and its educational and formative influence on the mental, ideological and moral-aesthetic development of the individual. The organization of the educational process in higher educational institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the training of personnel for the education system is based on the following didactic principles: unity of training and education; awareness and activity; scientific and systematic; connection between theory and practice; taking into account the age and individual characteristics of students; thoroughness and consolidation of acquired knowledge. In 2020, on December 31, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted Resolution No. 824 "On measures to improve the system of organizing the educational process in higher educational institutions"

According to the resolution, starting from the 2020/2021 academic year, the educational process in higher educational institutions gradually switched to a credit-module system. The transition to a credit-module system further raises the requirement for teacher training in organizing lessons. Accordingly, when organizing the educational process, teachers should organize the educational process in the following way, in place of authoritarian, explanatory and illustrative teaching methods, paying more attention to the organization of students' independent work. In place of mechanical assimilation of factual knowledge, mastering the ability to independently acquire new knowledge, using modern technologies of information interaction with modules of objects, processes, phenomena presented in subject environments.

However, it should be noted that the process of learning knowledge, as is known, is always the process of using this knowledge in any actions or activities. Outside of action, knowledge cannot be qualitatively acquired and used. If this is independently acquired knowledge, its effectiveness is much greater in the future of professional activity.

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